

Reproducing the Results from 'Measuring Influence on Instagram: A Network-Oblivious Approach' by Segev et al.

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This coursework from the lecture Experiment Design for Data Science at TU Wien aims to reproduce the results from the paper 'Measuring Influence on Instagram: A Network-Oblivious Approach' by Segev et al. [2]. The authors of the paper provided their data sources as csv files. However, they did neither provide any code nor any information about the parameters of clustering or regressors used in the paper. Our reproduction efforts lead in some cases to similar results, whereas in others the results differed significantly from the results provided in the paper. Effects of the random split of the data set in a 5-fold-cross-validation were tackled by application of 100 different random states and calculation of the standard deviation of these results to examine if our results are significantly different from the results in the paper.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Reproducibility, Social Media, Instagram, Influence, Ranking

1 ABOUT THE PAPER

The paper aims to find a model that allows for the measurement of the influence of Instagram users. Influence is defined as the number of views that a Instagram user achieves for his/her posts. A model using Random Forest and another one using Ridge Regression were compared against two baseline models. Each baseline was obtained using a linear regression model, one with the number of followers of a user as input and the other with the number of likes that a user reaches. Furthermore, the input data was split into groups by k-means clustering to apply multi-regression for influence prediction.

2 STRATEGIES

- First, we tried to gain deeper insight into the topic of the paper and the surrounding field of research. This is necessary to understand the approaches and goals of the paper.
- For the reproduction of the results we started by downloading the provided data source from the given source: https://klear.com/sigir/instagram_data.zip.
- Next, we tried to figure out what preprocessing steps described in the paper were already applied to the data and which are still necessary.
- In order to reproduce the regression results of the paper, we decided to use Python's scikit learn library [1]. The paper does not provide any information which package was used for the implementation of the regressors.
- Finally, we compared our results to the results from the paper and analyzed similarities and differences. Whenever obvious differences occurred we tried to find reasons for the mismatch.

3 DIFFICULTIES

The main cause for difficulties in the reproduction of the papers results was the missing source code. The paper states that for the Random Forest Regression and Ridge Regression, out-of-the-box models were used. However, since the code environment is not described, it's not clear what is meant exactly by out-of-the-box models. We decided to try to reproduce the results using scikit-learn [1], since it is the most common machine learning package.

Another problem was that the size of the data set described in the paper is slightly different from the data set that is downloadable under the provided link. This makes it difficult of understand if discrepancies to the paper arise from the differences of the data sets or from other reasons.

Especially problematic was the k-means clustering that is the basis for the multi-regression methods in the paper. In our reproduction efforts the k-means clustering was not successful/reasonable. This also prohibits the comparison to the results from multi-regression.

4 KEY FINDINGS

- The provided raw data is slightly differing from the raw data discussed in the paper.
- Data set characteristics and visualizations are mostly in accordance.
- Reproducing the k-means clustering did not lead to useful results. No information about the number of clusters was provided in the paper.
- Baseline models could be reproduced with comparable results.
- Results from different regressors are hard to reproduce since there is neither any information about the parameters, nor is there any information about the used development environment.
- Multi-regression can't be performed in a reasonable fashion because it is based on the k-means clustering.

5 RESULTS

5.1 Raw Data

Referring to the paper the dataset contains a total of 940439 posts by 115044 Instagrammers. Our analysis of the raw data showed a total of 1422894 posts by 114781. This means that the information from the paper is not correctly describing the data set or the data set was changed after the publication of the paper. The information is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Comparison of the data set characteristics.

	Paper	Reproduced	Difference
Instagrammers / No.	115044	114781	-263
Posts / No.	940439	1422894	482455

A graphical comparison of figures describing the data in the paper and our reproduced figures is visualized in Figure 1 and 2.

Fig. 1. Figures describing the raw data as shown in the paper.

Fig. 2. Reproduced figures from the provided raw data.

A comparison of the figures shows that the visualizations of the data sets lead to very similar results even though they differ in size. The green dashed line in both graphs represent the mean of the log-normal distribution. The paper states the mean of the log normal distribution to be at a value of 748 views, our calculated mean is at a value of 578. The reason for this deviation is probably the different size of the used data sets. A close observation of the log normal distributions shows that in our data set more data points can be observed at the lower end of the distribution.

5.2 Clustering

The paper stated that k-means clustering was applied to create groups of Instagrammers that can be used for multi regression at a later point. However, it is not clear what input parameters were used for the clustering and how many clusters were created. Since the paper argues that the clustering could improve the regression quality by means of separation of micro influencers and celebrities, we decided to go with a k value of 2. The clustering resulted in one group with only eight individuals with a very high level of engagements and views (celebrities) and another group that consists of all other individuals. The results of the clustering are shown in Figure 3.

In another approach we tried to find the optimal value for k using scikit-learns silhouette score. This resulted in an optimal k value of 1, which equals no clustering at all.

Fig. 3. Result of the k-means clustering.

5.3 Regression

Baseline. We reproduced the two baselines that were described in the paper. Both are linear regression models, one taking the average likes and one taking the average followers as input parameters to predict the influence. The performance of the baselines were estimated by a 5-fold cross validation in the paper. In order to eliminate the effect of the random seed we calculated 100 5-fold cross validations for each baseline (shuffling the data differently). Then we compared if the results from the paper are within the range of the standard deviation. Our results in comparison to the results in the paper are displayed in Table 2. The results stand in good accordance to the results from the paper. Besides the changes from the random seed, we can also expect some deviation due to the slightly different raw data.

Table 2. Results for the baseline models

5-CV	Paper - Mean	Reproduced - Mean	Reproduced - SD
Avg. Followers R2	0.211	0.262	0.059
Avg. Followers rs	0.757	0.753	0.000
Avg. Likes R2	0.666	0.682	0.022
Avg. Likes rs	0.859	0.845	0.000

Random Forest and Ridge Regression. Without any parameters nor development environment given, we decided to investigate if we obtain somewhat similar results using the out-of-the-box regression models from python's scikit-learn. The results from the out-of-the-box models differed severely from the results in the paper. To check if another setting for the hyperparameters is the reason for this difference, we tuned the alpha value for Ridge Regression. For a alpha value of 1500.0 we found the best results for Ridge Regression. Those results are displayed in Table 3. In general our results stand in good accordance to the results from the paper although small differences can be observed. Again, to tackle the influence of the random state we decided to use different random states for cross-validation and average the result. Results for Ridge Regression are an average of 50 random states and results from Random Forest are an average of 5 random states.

In addition to the full models, the paper also used reduced models that were obtained by feature elimination. As it was not stated which feature reduction algorithm was used, we decided to go with scikit-learn's Recursive Feature Elimination. For Ridge Regression the number of features was reduced to 2 from originally 8. The application of Recursive Feature Elimination to the Random

Forest models left them unchanged. The results for the reduced models are displayed in Table 3. For Ridge Regression the results are worse than the results described in the paper.

Table 3. Results for RR and RF models

5-CV	Paper (full)	Reproduced (full)	Paper (reduced)	Reproduced (reduced)
Random Forest R2	0.626	0.619 ± 0.066	-	-
Random Forest rs	0.869	0.868 ± 0.000	-	-
Ridge Regression R2	0.725	0.685 ± 0.051	0.723	0.590 ± 0.032
Ridge Regression rs	0.848	0.848 ± 0.000	0.818	0.763 ± 0.005

Summarized, the results show that we obtained somewhat comparable results for the full models. For the reduced models differences to the paper are obvious.

5.4 Multiregression

To reproduce the results from the multi-regression, we built regression models for each group that result from k-means clustering. It was immediately clear that this approach does not deliver useful results since the smaller cluster is only including 8 data points. That is far too little to build useful models for 5-fold-CV with Random Forest or Ridge Regression.

6 CONCLUSION

The authors of this paper provided a data set that could be taken as a basis to review their published results. A more in depth investigation of the raw data showed that the data set is slightly different from the data set described in the paper. Although the authors described roughly how they came up with their stated results, key information turned out to be missing. Besides the fact that no information was given about the development environment, the lack of any used model parameters is even more severe. Results from deterministic models like linear regression were reproducible. However, results from regressors that have different tuneable hyperparameters were not perfectly reproducible. The multi-regression based on k-means clustering could not be reasonably implemented.

7 PLATFORM INFORMATION

The raw data was obtained from https://klear.com/sigir/instagram_data.zip as described in the paper. Our reproduction efforts was conducted using Python and the sci-kit learn library. A Jupyter Notebook that contains all the information described in this report is available under <https://github.com/markus7800/ExDDSex2>.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Pedregosa, G. Varoquaux, A. Gramfort, V. Michel, B. Thirion, O. Grisel, M. Blondel, P. Prettenhofer, R. Weiss, V. Dubourg, J. Vanderplas, A. Passos, D. Cournapeau, M. Brucher, M. Perrot, and E. Duchesnay. 2011. Scikit-learn: Machine Learning in Python. *Journal of Machine Learning Research* 12 (2011), 2825–2830.
- [2] Noam Segev, Noam Avigdor, and Eytan Avigdor. 2018. Measuring influence on Instagram: a network-oblivious approach. In *The 41st International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research & Development in Information Retrieval*. 1009–1012.